

IoT Based wearable ECG monitoring system for Patient Emergency Condition

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KEYWORDS

Tele-ECG,
Heart Rate Monitoring,
Wearable Healthcare,
Remote Patient Monitoring,
Li-Fi Communication

ABSTRACT

This project presents a wearable Tele-ECG and heart rate (HR) monitoring system with an innovative architecture designed for real-time remote healthcare monitoring. The system incorporates a stretchable singlet embedded with textile electrodes (TEs), along with textile threads, snap fasteners, Velcro, sponges, and an ECG circuit for accurate biosignal acquisition. Additionally, smartphones, server, and web interface are integrated to facilitate seamless remote monitoring. To evaluate the effectiveness of the TE-based ECG system, an SMS-based ECG transmission mechanism has been implemented, achieving an average correlation of 99.23% between the recorded ECG signals. The system accurately plots ECG signals, calculates HR with a mean absolute percentage error of 1.83%, and displays the data in real time. The recorded ECG data is transmitted to a server, enabling physicians to analyze patient signals remotely via a web page or smartphone. For enhanced patient safety, the system includes an automatic alert mechanism. If the HR exceeds normal limits or the user presses the "HELP" button on the smartphone interface, an instant SMS notification is sent to the physician. Simultaneously, the system activates a flashing LED for additional alerting. This fast, uninterrupted telemonitoring system improves patient care and psychological reassurance, making it a promising tool for remote cardiac health management.

1. INTRODUCTION

Patient care demands on hospitals are on the rise in parallel with the growth of the world population and the

accompanying rise in chronic diseases. According to the mortality statistics recorded in 2015, 17.7 million people have lost their lives due to cardiovascular diseases in the

world. This number corresponds to 31% of the total number of deaths. Instrumentation and measurement (I and M) are a keystone to diagnose each disease. ECG measuring is quite important to examine and monitor a patient with heart problems. In a conventional ECG measuring system, In a recent study, Mahmud et al. [6] have proposed to measure instant ECG with a smartphone accessory, Ag/AgCl electrodes are attached to the body, with conductive gel at the electrode–skin interface, for signal acquisition to derive certain ECG leads. The conductive gel may be toxic and cause skin irritation and the Ag/AgCl electrodes may cause allergic reactions of the skin. Despite their high conductance initially, after prolonged use, Ag/AgCl, lose their adherence resulting in signal loss and requiring replacement. Therefore, the use of Ag/AgCl electrodes for extended periods of patient monitoring is not appropriate. As alternatives, dry metal electrodes have been used and some studies have explored textile electrode (TE) that has a minimal effect on patient's normal lifestyle.

The TE also has high contact conductivity that is essential for a reliable ECG acquisition. TE can be used to pick up ECG, EEG, and electromyogram (EMG) signals and they have been proven to be as reliable as Ag/AgCl electrodes. In normal conditions, the conductance of TE based ECG monitor is regarded as equivalent to Ag/AgCl. Humid conditions are advantageous rather than detrimental to TE-based monitor due to the electrolytic properties of sweat. The electrolyte includes molecules and ions. Therefore, it increases electrical conductivity. Nemati et al. [3] demonstrated a wireless ECG monitoring system which consisted of a belt stretched inside a T-shirt and equipped with three capacitive electrodes, Contactless ECG sensors provide the convenience of monitoring in nonhospital environments. Diverse ECG measurement systems have been reported including systems that can be fixed to chair bed or can be adapted to clothes. Nemati et al demonstrated a wireless ECG monitoring system which consisted of a belt stretched inside a T-shirt and equipped with three capacitive electrodes, where the ECG measuring is transmitted to a PC, requiring the user to own a PC. However, once this proposed system is preferred, the patients can use their existing cell phone for monitoring the vital signs collected ECG signals using two electric potential integrated circuit sensors

fitted in a phone case and were able to transmit the signal with a microcontroller through Bluetooth low energy (BLE) and displayed the ECG signal on a cell phone. They also use smartphone memory to save ECG data, which is not appropriate for multiple usages due to limited data storage.

2.LITERATURE REVIEW

A.TITLE: "A wireless wearable ECG sensor for longterm applications" AUTHOR: E. Nemati, M. J. Deen, and T. Mondal.

ECG measuring is quite important to examine and monitor a patient with heart problems. In a conventional ECG measuring system, Ag/AgCl electrodes are attached to the body, with conductive Manuscript received June 11, 2018; revised January 3, 2019; accepted January 5, 2019. This work was supported by the Republic of Turkey Ministry of Development, Istanbul Development Agency through the Innovative and Creative Istanbul Financial Support Program under Project TR10/16YNY/0136. Color versions of one or more of the figures in this paper are available online at Digital Object Identifier gel at the electrode–skin interface, for signal acquisition to derive certain ECG leads. The conductive gel may be toxic and cause skin irritation and the Ag/AgCl electrodes may cause allergic reactions of the skin. Despite their high conductance initially, after prolonged use, Ag/AgCl, lose their adherence resulting in signal loss and requiring replacement. Chamadiya et al. [8] performed ECG measurements with electrodes fitted on stretchers, wheelchairs, and patient beds Therefore, the use of Ag/AgCl electrodes for extended periods of patient monitoring is not appropriate. As alternatives, dry metal electrodes have been used and some studies have explored textile electrode (TE) that has a minimal effect on patient's normal lifestyle. The TE also has high contact conductivity that is essential for a reliable ECG acquisition. TE can be used to pick up ECG, EEG, and electromyogram (EMG) signals and they have been proven to be as reliable as Ag/AgCl electrodes. In normal conditions, the conductance of TE based ECG monitor is regarded as equivalent to Ag/AgCl. Humid conditions are advantageous rather than detrimental to TE-based monitor due to the electrolytic properties of sweat. The electrolyte includes molecules and ions. Therefore, it increases electrical conductivity. Contactless ECG sensors provide the convenience of

monitoring in nonhospital environments. Diverse ECG measurement systems have been reported including systems that can be fixed to chair, bed or can be adapted to clothes demonstrated a wireless ECG monitoring system which consisted of a belt stretched inside a T-shirt.

B. TITLE: "Unobtrusive Sensing of Psychophysical Parameters" AUTHORS: M. Ouwerkerk, F. Pasveer, and G. Langereis.

One of the main goals of this project is to provide maximum convenience to the user or patient during ECG measurements, especially for prolonged use. Therefore, special consideration is taken regarding two interfaces: the patient-sensor and sensor-cardiologist interfaces. A convenient interface between the body and the sensor can be realized using a non-contact ECG sensing method. Alternatives for wet ECG that potentially provide comfortable patient-sensor interface are dry-electrode or capacitively-coupled ECG (CC-ECG) methods.

3. EXISTING SYSTEM

This system consists of Bluetooth module and it is used to transmit about the condition of patient's brief. It Can't able to transmit for a long range.

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed system is a portable, wearable Tele-ECG monitoring system designed to provide real-time health monitoring for individuals, particularly elderly patients and individuals with cardiovascular conditions. By integrating IoT-based remote monitoring, biometric authentication, and multi-sensor data acquisition, this system ensures enhanced safety, ease of use, and continuous tracking of vital signs in both hospital and home settings. The block diagram of the proposed system is shown below (Figure 1)

Figure 1: Block diagram of the proposed system

The system comprises several key components:

ECG Sensor (AD8232 or equivalent):

- Captures the **heart's electrical activity** and monitors the **heart rate (HR)**.
- Provides real-time ECG waveform data, allowing **early detection of arrhythmias or abnormalities**.
- The ECG sensor is integrated into a **smart wearable garment**, ensuring continuous monitoring without discomfort.

Pressure and Humidity Sensors:

- A **pressure sensor** monitors **blood pressure fluctuations**, helping detect conditions such as **hypertension or hypotension**.
- A **humidity and temperature sensor** tracks **body temperature and environmental conditions**, crucial for **detecting fever, dehydration, or heat stress**.

LED-Based Visual Alert System:

- LEDs provide **immediate visual feedback** on vital signs:
 - **Green LED:** Normal values.
 - **Yellow LED:** Slight abnormality, requiring attention.
 - **Red LED:** Critical condition, triggering alerts.

Arduino-Based Processing Unit:

- The **Arduino microcontroller** processes sensor data in real-time, analyzes trends, and triggers necessary alerts.
- It ensures seamless communication between **sensors, display units, and IoT modules**.

IoT-Based Remote Monitoring:

- The system utilizes **Wi-Fi connectivity** to transmit ECG, heart rate, blood pressure, and temperature data to a **mobile application or cloud service**.
- Healthcare professionals or caregivers can access **live data, historical trends, and alerts** through a **secure web interface or mobile app**.
- If any vital sign crosses predefined thresholds, an **automatic SMS/email notification** is sent to **physicians or emergency contacts**.

Biometric Authentication Using ECG Signals:

- To enhance security, the system incorporates **biometric authentication** based on the user's **unique ECG signal patterns**.
- This feature ensures that **only authorized individuals can access and modify health data**, preventing **unauthorized access or data manipulation**.

The sequence of the events of the proposed system are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Sequence of events of the proposed system

Advantages of the Proposed System:

- **Fast Response & Continuous Monitoring:** Ensures real-time detection of health anomalies with instant alerts to users and caregivers.
- **Easy Integration in Hospitals & Homes:** The wearable, non-invasive design makes it ideal for both clinical and home healthcare environments.
- **Enhanced Safety for Elderly and At-Risk Individuals:** Continuous monitoring helps prevent sudden cardiac events, providing peace of mind to patients and their families.
- **IoT-Enabled Data Storage & Remote Access:** Allows secure, cloud-based storage of medical history, enabling trend analysis and long-term monitoring by healthcare professionals.
- **Portable & User-Friendly Interface:** Designed to be lightweight, easy to wear, and simple to operate using a mobile app.

5. RESULTS& DISCUSSION

A portable wearable TELE-ECG monitoring system enables continuous, real-time electrocardiogram (ECG) monitoring outside clinical settings. It is designed to provide remote health monitoring, ensuring timely detection of arrhythmias, heart rate abnormalities, or other cardiovascular conditions. The system transmits data wirelessly to healthcare professionals, enabling prompt analysis and intervention. Advantages of such a

system include improved patient compliance, convenience, and the ability to detect heart-related issues at an early stage. However, challenges include data security concerns, the need for reliable wireless connectivity, and potential limitations in sensor accuracy during physical activity or long-term use. Despite these issues, TELE-ECG systems offer promising potential for managing chronic heart conditions and reducing hospital visits.

Figure 3: Hardware kit implementation

The hardware kit implementation (Figure 3) based on Arduino, an ECG sensor (Figure 4), and an LCD involves using an Arduino microcontroller to process the electrical signals detected by the ECG sensor and display the results on an LCD screen. The ECG sensor, such as the AD8232, is connected to the Arduino to capture heart activity signals through electrodes placed on the body. The Arduino processes these signals, amplifies and filters them, and then displays the real-time ECG waveform or heart rate data on the LCD. The LCD provides an easy way to visualize the data locally, making it ideal for portable and wearable heart health monitoring systems.

Figure 4: implementation of ECG Sensor

The hardware kit implementation based on Arduino and an ECG sensor for measuring values involves connecting an ECG sensor, like the AD8232, to an Arduino board to capture the electrical signals generated by the heart. The ECG sensor outputs an analog signal that corresponds to the heart's electrical activity, which is then read by the Arduino's analog input pin. The Arduino processes this signal by filtering out noise, amplifying the ECG waveform, and performing basic analysis, such as detecting heart rate.

The ECG sensor, such as the AD8232, generates an analog output that is proportional to the electrical activity of the heart. When interfaced with an Arduino, the sensor's output is typically read via an analog input pin, which converts the voltage levels into digital values that can be processed. Below is an example of how you can interpret and measure the values from the ECG sensor in a table format.

ECG Sensor Measurement Table (Example)

Time (ms)	ECG Signal (Analog Value)	Heart Rate (BPM)	ECG Waveform Features
0	512	-	Resting baseline (P-wave start)
50	550	-	R-wave peak
100	480	-	S-wave descent
150	460	-	T-wave rise
200	520	-	Relaxing baseline (End of T-wave)
250	510	75	-
300	530	75	-
350	500	75	-
400	515	75	-

6. CONCLUSIONS

The proposed wearable Tele-ECG monitoring system has been designed to enhance continuous ECG monitoring by addressing the limitations of existing devices. Through the careful selection of electronic components and an efficient software implementation, the system offers high autonomy, compact size, and lightweight design, ensuring ease of use and improved patient comfort. By integrating a microcontroller, the system overcomes the challenges of previous research projects and commercial solutions. The microcontroller digitizes ECG signals, facilitates seamless data exchange via Bluetooth, and supports advanced ECG signal processing such as heart rate detection and R-R interval analysis. Additionally, the system's adaptability enables its use in various healthcare settings, catering to different monitoring needs.

Future Scope

Future advancements in the Portable Wearable Tele-ECG Monitoring System will focus on expanding its

capabilities to provide more comprehensive health monitoring. Planned enhancements include the integration of temperature and humidity sensors to monitor the body's internal conditions, alongside an ECG and pressure sensor to track blood pressure and heart rate fluctuations. The system will also feature real-time mobile alerts, ensuring that critical health parameters are instantly communicated to caregivers and medical professionals. These improvements will further enhance remote patient monitoring, early disease detection, and personalized healthcare solutions, making the system a versatile and indispensable tool in modern telemedicine.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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